

Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Site-Specific Drug Delivery: Synthesis, Functionalization, and Biomedical Applications

Swetha K*, Madhanraja R, Mohanapriya M, Indhuja K, Sumathi P, Varshini G

Kmch college of pharmacy, Kovai estate kalapatti road, Coimbatore -641048

ABSTRACT

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) have garnered significant attention as a promising platform for drug delivery in biomedical applications due to their exceptional structural and functional properties. With a high surface area, uniform and tunable pore sizes, and ease of surface functionalization, MSNs enable the efficient encapsulation, protection, and controlled release of therapeutic agents. Recent advancements have demonstrated their potential to improve drug bioavailability and target specific cells, showing particular promise in cancer therapy. For instance, functionalizing MSNs with targeting ligands, such as folic acid, has enhanced cellular uptake and demonstrated increased cytotoxic effects on cancer cells. Additionally, MSNs' ability to overcome drug resistance barriers, particularly in treating bacterial infections, highlights their role in tackling key challenges in pharmaceutical development. Their inherent biocompatibility and flexibility for modification also allow MSNs to serve various therapeutic and diagnostic applications, establishing them as a versatile tool in Nano medicine. As research progresses, the combination of MSNs with other nanomaterials may offer innovative approaches for "smart" drug delivery, potentially transforming treatment methodologies across multiple medical fields. This overview lays the groundwork for exploring the multifaceted roles of MSNs in advancing drug delivery efficacy and their potential to revolutionize healthcare solutions.

KEYWORDS: *Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), Drug delivery systems, Controlled drug release, targeted drug delivery.*

1. INTRODUCTION¹

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) have emerged as a versatile platform for drug delivery in biomedical applications due to their unique structural properties and tunable characteristics. With a high surface area, uniform pore size, and the ability to functionalize their surfaces, MSNs facilitate the encapsulation and controlled release of therapeutic agents. Recent studies have highlighted their potential in enhancing drug bioavailability and targeting specific cells, particularly in cancer treatment. For instance, the decoration of MSNs with targeting ligands, such as folic acid, has shown promise in increasing cellular uptake and improving cytotoxic effects against cancer cells. The ability of MSNs to overcome drug resistance barriers, particularly in bacterial infections, further underscores their significance in pharmaceutical development. Additionally, their biocompatibility and ease of modification enable a broad range of therapeutic and diagnostic applications, positioning MSNs at the forefront of nanomedicine. As research continues to evolve, the integration of MSNs with other nanomaterials is expected to yield innovative strategies for smart drug delivery systems. This introduction sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the multifaceted roles of MSNs in enhancing drug delivery efficacy and their potential to revolutionize treatment methodologies across various medical fields.

2. SYNTHESIS²

The features of MSNs, such as their shape, specific surface area, particle size, and pore size, are determined by the preparation technique and different reaction circumstances. Furthermore, MSNs include a mesoporous structure in the nanoparticles; these methods of synthesis are classified as either soft or hard templating procedures. The following are a few techniques utilized in the creation of MSNs.

2.1. Stober process

Based on the sol-gel procedure, the Stober approach has been extensively studied in the synthesis of MSNs. It is possible to perform the Stober process in basic, acidic, or neutral environments. In order to generate the ordered structure (gel) of the polymer, the process primarily requires the hydrolysis and condensation processes of alkoxide monomers in a solution (sol). The concentration of the alkoxide group and Si/H₂O in molar ratios determines the hydrolysis reaction. When the concentration of pore templates exceeds the critical micellar concentration (CMC), they can usually join into a self-assembled structure and transform into micelles. Moreover, silica condenses around the template to form a silica barrier that covers the micelle's surface. Finally, calcination is carried out by refluxing, or heating the product at 600 °C for six hours in a muffle furnace.

2.2. Evaporation-induced self-assembly (EISA)

Evaporation induced self-assembly (EISA) is another well-known method for creating MSNs. In this method, the reactant concentration varies all the way through the reaction. As a result, the liquid crystal template and silica precursors are formed. The appropriate concentration of the precursor formulation can be created by first combining ethanol, water, and a surfactant. This formulation converts to homogeneously dispersed droplets with the help of injection using an aerosol generator.

2.3. Ultrasonic assisted synthesis

MSNs can also be created using ultrasonic synthesis. It can be done with a cationic surfactant and a silica source in acidic media. The MSNs produced using this method have excellent ordered structure, pore volume ($>1 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$), and specific surface area ($>1100 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). When considering alternative synthesis techniques, ultra-sonication -assisted synthesis has the potential to drastically reduce manufacturing time. As a result, this procedure is renowned for its quick MSN synthesis and great efficiency. It does have several drawbacks, though, like a low yield and reduced structural homogeneity.

2.4. Microwave-assisted method

The fabrication of materials containing porous and ceramic oxide components is often aided by the microwave-assisted process. Comparing this procedure to other methods, it is both simpler and less expensive. Using CTAB as a structure-directing agent, it is utilized to synthesize MCM-41, which has an ordered mesoporous structure. The reaction vessel's temperature may be exceeded by the heat produced by the microwave during the operation. The stability of prepared MSNs and a high-quality mesoporous structure are provided by this approach.

2.5. Synthesis of mesoporous silica nanoparticles

An already optimized procedure was applied to generate MSNs. In summary, 275 μL of NH_4OH solution was added to a solution containing 75 mg of CTAB that had been dissolved in 30 mL of distilled water at 45 $^\circ\text{C}$. After that, two hours of vigorous stirring at 300 rpm with 125 μL of TEOS added all at once. Amicon ultra centrifugal filters were used to centrifuge the clear solution that was produced. The CTAB surfactant template was eliminated from the silica nanoparticles by refluxing them with 1% acidic methanol for four hours at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$. To extract MSNs, the suspension of nanoparticles was centrifuged and repeatedly cleaned with methanol.

2.6. Synthesis of MSN from Dye Encapsulation

In order to obtain a 1M concentration, the relevant amounts of fluorescein (FI) dye are dissolved in 10 mL EtOH to create a fluorescein ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$) dye solution. This solution is then mixed with 0.1 mg of the previously made MSNs powder. After that, the mixture is shaken at room temperature for a full day. Following the incorporation of dye into the nanopores, the dye-encapsulated solid MSN were separated by centrifugation and extensively cleaned with ethanol to eliminate any remaining free dye molecules as well as those that remained adhered to the MSN's exterior.

2.7. Biogenic synthesis

Fig.1. calcination process

As the name implies, biological silica sources, mostly rice and wheat husk, are used to synthesize MSN. These sources are renewable. To make this, first boil the husk in an acidic water solution to get rid of any extraneous particles, then wash and let it dry for the entire night. Based on calculations, this dried husk is expected to yield amorphous silica nanoparticles (NPs) that dissolve readily in NaOH solution, providing sodium silicate solution as a precursor silica source. It produces NP precipitate when combined with a surfactant-rich media under the right circumstances, while evenly sized MSN are obtained upon template removal.¹⁰

3. MSNs WITH UNIQUE FEATURES TO FIGHT AGAINST BACTERIAL INFECTIONS³

3.1. Improving delivery of antibiotics by MSNs

Antimicrobials can be stacked into the mesoporous or center system of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) by their special structure, or they can be immobilized on the surface through covalent or noncovalent intuitive, making MSNs profoundly flexible sedate carriers. Joining anti-microbial offers numerous focal points such as control over medicate discharge, expanded warm steadiness, and the plausibility of site-specific activated discharge. Chemical intelligence between Si and Goodness permits antimicrobial to tie covalently to the surface or permeable dividers of MSN. The better bactericidal movement was illustrated by MSNs conjugated with triclosan, an FDA-approved pharmaceutical, than triclosan alone. However, since the chemical intuition included, covalent holding is regularly complicated and improper for numerous medicines.

Fig. 2. The schematic illustrations and corresponding TEM images of silica nanoparticles based on structural morphology (A), shape (B) and porous structure

Antibiotics can also be encapsulated in the pores or adsorbed onto the surface of MSNs through solvent evaporation. Polymyxin B (PMB), a last-resort antibiotic for treating gram-negative pathogens resistant to most other drugs, has been loaded onto MSNs to achieve sustained release. This approach not only prolongs the antimicrobial efficacy of PMB but also helps reduce its side effects. Additionally, the adsorbed PMB is more effective against bacteria than the free drug, likely due to higher local concentrations around the bacterial cells. MSNs also adhere strongly to bacterial walls, interacting with the negatively charged silica surface and the positively charged peptidoglycans in gram-positive bacteria. Loading MSNs with lysozymes significantly enhanced antibacterial effects by breaking down bacterial cell walls, as lysozymes cleave the β -1,4 bonds between N-acetylmuramic acid and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine. However, larger pores may be needed in MSNs to accommodate the larger size of lysozymes. For instance, Xu and colleagues used hollow MSNs (HMSNs) to increase lysozyme loading (around 350 mg/g), resulting in a more sustained release and stronger antibacterial action. Since many antibiotics must penetrate bacterial cell walls and membranes to reach the cytoplasm, particle size is a key factor. MSNs larger than 100 nm tend to adhere to bacterial surfaces rather than being taken up by bacteria. Therefore, improving the effectiveness of antibiotic-loaded MSNs has led to a focus on surface modifications, stimuli-responsive drug release, and synergistic effects with metal ions, all of which are explored in greater detail in the following sections.¹¹

3.2. Targeting delivery to bacteria using surface-modified MSNs

As of late, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) have picked up noteworthy consideration in biomedicine due to their poisonous quality, improved sedate bioavailability, and improved restorative adequacy. Endeavours have been made to alter the surface of MSNs to move forward sedate conveyance proficiency and anticipate untimely discharge. Two common strategies for surface alternation are post-grafting, which includes connecting utilitarian layers to sialon bunches using covalent or non-covalent bonds, and co-condensation, where useful species are joined amid the amalgamation of MSNs. Surface charge plays a key part in nanoparticle-bacteria intuition, as adversely charged bacterial dividers impact attachment. For occurrence, coating MSNs with polycationic dendrimers has made strides in bacterial film porousness and anti-microbial impacts. Altered MSNs have been utilized to combat multi drug resistance (MDR) by upgrading anti-microbial take-up and bypassing bacterial efflux pumps. Biomimetic approaches, such as coating MSNs with bacterial external films, encourage the increment of their partially with microscopic organisms. For illustration, redox-responsive MSNs have been outlined to discharge vancomycin at disease locales, upgrading antibacterial impacts. Besides, silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) hybridized with MSNs maintain anti-microbial activity by

avoiding conglomeration and advancing ceaseless silver particle discharge. Metal particles also synergize with MSNs for moved-forward biofilm infiltration and destruction of antibiotic-resistance microbes. These headways highlight the potential of MSNs in overcoming challenges related to sedate conveys and bacterial resistance.

3.3. Enhancing antibacterial performance by tailoring morphology of MSNs

Fig. 3. Schematic illustrations of fabrication of outer membrane coated MSNs and antibacterial mechanisms. (a) The outer membrane vesicles (OMVs) were isolated from *E. coli* and then coated onto rifampicin loaded MSNs (Rif@MSN). (b) The biomimetic MSNs can target the *E. coli* infected mice and exhibit stronger effects by improving targeting efficiency and uptake, followed by killing *E. coli*. However, this system did not work on Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus*.¹²

Later considerations have investigated the effect of nanoparticle shape on their physicochemical properties and in vivo behaviour, with MSNs (mesoporous silica nanoparticles) getting critical consideration due to their tunable morphology. MSNs have been manufactured in different shapes, counting circle, bars, ellipsoids, and star-like structures, permitting analyte to explore their impact on anti-bacterial action. For occasion, Ahmed F.Halbus and colleagues created MSNs with a harsh surface that appeared to improve antibacterial impacts on *Rhodococcus* and *E.coli* due to bacterial layer disturbance. Moreover, rod-shaped MSNs with a higher view point proportion, doped with silver particles and coated with chitosan, showed more grounded bacterial restraint. The arrangement of their long pivot with bacterial layers increases their cell film's unsettling influence. Moreover, permeable structures play a vital part, as harsh, spiky surface taking after infection particles upgrade grip to bacterial cells, driving to higher medicate stacking and delayed antibacterial movement, especially in biofilm treatment.

3.4. Combating bacterial infections by metal-MSNs nanocomposites

Ranjith kumar kankala and colleagues looked into progressions in metal-MSNs nanocomposites (M-MSNs), centering on their species with anti-bacterial medications. Combining metal species with MSNs upgrades their execution by stabilizing MSNs and anticipating the accumulation of metal nanoparticles (MSPs). Different strategies, such as cooperative self-assembly and formation exchange, have been utilized to build these crossovers. For occurrence, ultrasmall silver nanoclusters (Ag-NCs) appear higher bacterial effectiveness due to expanded surface region, but they confront steadiness challenges. To address this, Ag-NCs were implanted into MSNs to guarantee supported Ag+discharge and avoid conglomeration. Moreover, copper-doped MSNs stacked with tetracycline were created for overcoming multi drug -resistant microbes (MDR), utilizing pH-responsive coordination intelligence. The synergistic activity of metal particles and antimicrobial altogether move forward antibacterial efficacy.

3.5. Antibacterial effect of MSNs activated by therapeutic aids

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) have potential application as restorative help, particularly in treating disease. Whereas immaculate MSNs are by and large considered to have cytotoxicity and restricted antibacterial properties. They still upgrade existing medicines for irresistible maladies by tending to issue like cytotoxicity, Geno toxicity, and haemolytic impacts regularly connected with metal nanoparticles. Later ponders investigated the utilization of MSNs as sensitizers in combination with helpful ultrasounds light (USI) for antimicrobial purpose. It was found that combining silicon nanoparticles with USI created a synergistic impact, upgrading bacterial concealment by *E. coli*. This impact is described to the cavitation handle, where the nanoparticles cause bacterial layer aperture. The joint activity of ultrasound

and nanoparticles comes about in more noteworthy changes compared to either treatment utilized alone. In addition, adjusting the surface of MSNs with dextran advanced boosted bacterial restraint by advancing more grounded attachment to the bacterial surface, powder the harm caused by cavitation. These discoveries illustrate MSNs potential as promising antimicrobial agents.

4. FUNCTIONALIZED MSNs⁴

Various approaches have been used to modify MSN with ligands to achieve controlled or sustained release of bioactive molecules, better cell compatibility, enhancing targeting and regulation of biological action. Improvements in surface functionalization in MSNs has enhanced their ability. It emphasizes on modified ligands that react to stimuli like pH, light, temperature, ultrasound and magnetic fields. It also acts on particular receptors to optimize biocompatibility, biodegradability, excretion and targets the bioactive molecule release which reduces the harmful effects on the body.

4.1. Temperature-responsive functionalized MSNs

Temperature is a commonly utilized and easily controllable stimulus for activating MSN delivery systems in biomedical applications. Original MSNs are made up of inorganic materials and are unresponsive to temperature. The MSNs delivery systems stay inactive at the normal body temperature (37°C) but activate at higher temperature at specific tumour areas, which is especially used alongside hyperthermia therapy. This activation is due to changes in the polymeric ligands, enabling targeted, controlled, and sustained delivery that reduces systemic toxicity. Poly (N-isopropyl acrylamide) (PNIPAM) is the most widely recognized thermal sensitive polymer which has been associated with heat sensitive properties of MSNs. The temperature-sensitive behaviour of PNIPAM which is used to regulate the release of bioactive molecules from the pores of MSNs in two different ways. In the first method, bioactive molecules are filled into MSNs pores. The soluble PNIPAM are blocked by a layer of “gatekeeper” soluble bonded PNIPAM at temperatures below the lower critical solution temperature (LCST). This system is more suitable for MSNs with smaller pore sizes and longer polymer chains.

4.2. Magnetic field responsive functionalized MSNs

Magnetic field is a widely accessible and definite approach to handle the response of magnetic materials. Super paramagnetic ferric oxide nanoparticles (M-Fe-NPs), which includes Fe₃O₄ and Fe₂O₃ are the most common sources of magnetic materials that have been most commonly used in biomedical applications like in viva magnetic resonance imaging, magnetic mediated hyperthermia that helps in delivery of therapeutic agents and cancer treatment. Hyperthermia is a significant feature of M-Fe-NPs when exposed to an external magnetic field (EMF). The generated heat is utilized to control the liberation of the payload or to detach capping structures, thereby directing the release of bioactive molecules. The surface of MSNs is capped with M-Fe-NPs which inhibits the premature diffusion of bioactive molecules. MSNs were altered using single-stranded DNA, which was filled with payloads and capped with complementary DNA-conjugated magnetic iron nanoparticles (M-Fe-NPs). The binding of the two DNA strands securely seals the MSNs' pores, inhibiting the payload from being released. When an external magnetic field (EMF) is applied, the hyperthermia effect raises the temperature, causing the double-stranded DNA to melt, breaking the seal and enabling the payload to be released. This process of DNA assembly and disassembly is reversible, enabling controlled "on-off" release form.

4.3. Ultrasound responsive functionalized MSNs

Ultrasound (US) have been predominantly used in diagnosing in image form which is poorly absorbed by water and tissue. This stimulus helps in directing the response of the MNSs which helps to optimize the activity in delivery of bioactive molecules and imaging. The porous structure of MSNs allows for ultrasound imaging which acts as a theranostic tool to help deliver insulin-like growth factor (IGF) and inhibits stem cell death. Functionalized MSNs effectively release hydrophobic drugs and result in significant cytolysis while enhancing the contrast of ultrasound imaging. The release of the hydrophobic pyrene model drug, co-encapsulated with liquid perfluorohexane (PFH) which are incorporated in the pores of Au-doped H-MSNs and capped with PEG that is predominantly improved when subjected to ultrasound irradiation due to the hyperthermia effect and the cavitation of PFP. This resulted in notable cytolysis and enhanced ultrasound imaging contrast in both in vitro and in vivo settings. Moreover, the inclusion of the PFH bubble generator advanced ultrasound image resolution, enabling precise targeting of treatment areas in tumor tissue. Functionalization of MSNs has been done by hydrophobic floured alkyl or alkyl that contributes US responsive bubbles on high intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) exposure which are formed by the entrapment of air in the dried pores. It can be employed for effective cancer cell elimination in conjunction with ultrasound in the form of synergistic effect.

4.4. Electric field responsive functionalized MSNs

Electric fields are abundantly present and have been extensively used in our daily life and also in medical devices to enhance the health conditions. Electric fields are used to change to the coated biomolecules which are delivered from MSNs. Bipolar 4-(3-

cyanophenyl) butylene molecules are bonded to the inner surfaces of the MSN pores and work as nano impellers. When an external electric field is applied, allowing for controlled release of ibuprofen (IBU). By adjusting the frequency of the electric field, the swinging rate of these bipolar molecules can be controlled, which helps in modulating the release rate of the encapsulated IBU.

4.5. pH responsive functionalized MSNs

pH is an important factor of the body's biological fluids, blood and tissues which has the pH of 7.4 and at some state, like inflammation and tumor sites (pH ~ 6.8), cytosols (pH 6.5-5.5) and lysosomes (pH 5.5-4.5). Bare MSNs can promote the release of loaded molecules like DOX at low pH by weakening electrostatic interactions, but this triggering effect is usually weak and slow. Moreover, the loaded molecules might unintentionally leak out of the MSNs, which lead to systemic toxicity. To stop premature leakage and develop a more effective triggering method, different strategies have been used to functionalize the MSNs. Surface of MSNs containing functionalization molecules such as carboxylic acid (COOH) or amine groups is one of the easiest forms to incorporate pH responsive compounds of MSNs. The functionalized MSNs are coated with payloads which are stable for a long period of time in the physiological pH that prevents cell toxicity. Acid sensitive functional groups are unchangeable at neutral pH and it gets unstable at acidic pH of cytoplasm and tumor tissues. This pH responsive group has been used to facilitate the activity of MSNs.

4.6. Redox agent responsive functionalized MSNs

Glutathione (GSH), dithiothreitol (DTT), and tris(2-carboxyethyl) phosphate are the some of the examples of redox molecules which possess the capability to deteriorate the disulphide bond (-S-S-) in the aqueous media into two thiol groups. In cancer cells, the GSH concentration is higher (approximately 3-fold) than the normal healthy cells. In cancer therapy, the majority of synthesized MSNs are used as nanocarriers. Therefore it has led to better bioactivity and reduces cell toxicity.

4.7. ROS responsive functionalized MSNs

The reactive oxygen species (ROS) like H₂O₂ which takes part in the metabolic reaction at an increased rate with some of the diseases such as heart failure, Alzheimer's and in the aging and inflammation process. Phenylboronic acid bonded MSNs were filled with bioactive molecules and capping was done to adjacent diol groups which also contain human IgG and β -D-glu-cose-AuNPs to reduce the diffusion of the payload. Phenyl Borate ester bonds are divided from the phenol groups and the capped molecules get removed from the surface of the MSNs in the presence of H₂O₂ in the local environment which leads to the better release rate of payloads.

4.8. Enzyme responsive functionalized MSNs

Enzymes are the most essential macromolecular biological catalysts in the living cells which are associated with cellular metabolic processes and biochemical reactions. Surface of MSNs is functionalized with different ligands which form enzyme-induced intracellular controlled delivery of bioactive molecules. It is commonly used in toxic chemotherapeutic in cancer treatment.

4.9. ATP responsive functionalized MSNs

The multifunctional nucleotide is adenosine-5'-triphosphate (ATP) which is integrated with many biological operations in the living cells, it includes nerve impulse propagation, muscle contraction, formation and breakdown of biomolecules, cellular functions, and membrane transport. ATP-aptamer has ideal features and chemical structure to bond with ATP molecules and has been used in ATP regulating the liberation of bioactive molecules from the MSNs.

4.10. Cell targeting functionalized MSNs

In chemotherapeutics, biological transfer of toxic biomolecules by MSN-form nanocarriers which could lead to cellular toxicity. MSNs have been functionalized with particular cell focusing ligands to confine the nanocarriers at the exact cells and tissues. YGR KRRQRR sequence is present in TAT-peptide get bonded to the cancer cells present importin receptors and gets into the nuclei through the cell nuclear pore complex and then it gets bind to the MSNs in which the cancer cells are focused to distribute chemotherapeutic or cellular DNA harvesting.

4.11. Glucose responsive functionalized MSNs

The vital component that is distributed in the blood of animals as blood sugar is glucose. In diabetic patients, the blood sugar is extensively increased and essential signals are used to control the distribution of insulin such as a protein for diabetic treatment and therapeutic molecules.

4.12. Multiple signals responsive functionalized MSNs

The response functionalized MSNs present in the tissue environment are mostly regulated by bio signals. For example, cancer cells are alive at low pH and are abundant with redox agents, enzymes, and focused receptors. Additionally, the external signals include temperature, magnetic and electric fields, and light is available and easy to regulate. Thus, MSN's functionalization with ligands produces better synergetic effects and reduces the cellular toxicity of biomolecules.

5. CDDS AND ITS TYPES⁵

Ligand directed drug delivery via targeted drug delivery which has been taken place in a particular cell, tissue, organ whereas the drug gets released from the pores of MSNs into the blood circulation without reaching the particular site of tissue and uptake of drugs through the healthy cells can lead to unknown side effects through Nano system type of drug delivery. Pores of MSNs are covered by stimuli responsive (caps gatekeepers), this may help in regulating the release of drug from the embedded cargo which helps in controlling the liberation of drugs and destruction of payloads thus lowers the cellular toxicity and enhances the therapeutic effects. The gatekeepers are activated by internal triggers such as enzymes, redox and pH and external triggers such as photo irradiation, temperature and magnetism which involve breaking the pores to liberate the drug from the payloads. Sialon subunits are present on the surface of ligand functionalization MSNs that helps in focusing the particular site of unhealthy cells and the signals hits the gatekeepers to liberate the drug to the particular tissue.

5.1. pH response

The pH sensitive drug delivery acts on the principle of change of pH in normal and unhealthy tissues by Nano-system. The Nano carrier and capping agent is connected by pH sensitive linkage, when the certain is reached it activates the nanocomposite and the drug is delivered at a particular site. Shakeran et al. have executed the idea in which the MSN was prepared, filled with methotrexate and it was functionalized with chitosan (CHS) and 3-tri-ethoxy-silylpropylamine that was linked between CHS molecules and the surface of MSNs, therefore the nanoparticles are positively charged with smooth spherical methodology (>100 nm in size). By this approach, the chitosan covering MSNs enhances the uptake of drugs by the tissues and lowers the sustainability of breast cancer tissues at reduced dose. The nanoparticles show increased toxicity when compared to drug free and free drug nanoparticles.

5.2. Redox response

The principal antioxidant Glutathione (GSH) is a tripeptide (consisting of glutamate, glycine and cysteine) which is present in cell organelles involved in scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitrogen species. Glutathione is the cofactor in the functioning of cellular enzymatic processes. In scavenging reactive oxygen species, the glutathione is reduced and oxidized glutathione. The excessively produced glutathione is used in limiting the drug delivery from MSNs which were filled with P-glycoprotein inhibitor quercetin and paclitaxel and that was bonded by disulfide linkage and coated with chondroitin sulfate.

5.3. Enzyme response

The enzymes are catalysts in certain circumstances of temperature, pressure within the cell, pH and the rate of chemical reactions. In the body, the enzymes are present in certain tissues or cells that include phosphatases, glycosides and protease and they are in increased levels in inflamed tissues and cancerous cells. Enzymes of particular ligands have been bonded with drug-filled nanoparticles that target the unhealthy cells, thus enhancing the efficacy of the drug. Different types of nanosized enzyme responsive drug delivery systems are made up of lipids, inorganic or organic hybrids, liposomes and polymers.

5.4. Reactive oxygen species response

Oxidative stress is the imbalance of oxidants and antioxidants that supports the oxidants is the statement which was defined by Dean Jones and Helmut Sies. Extreme cell destruction along with many diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, neurodegenerative diseases, inflammation, cerebrovascular diseases and diabetes and other injured sites. Different ROS-response carriers are used at the sites of increased levels of reactive oxygen species. Polylactic acid is used in destruction of reactive oxygen species. Resveratrol is filled in MSNs and capped with polylactic acid and is used in targeting the brain.

5.5. Magnetic response

MNP are generally studied for site specific drug delivery and diagnosis via external applied magnetic signals to the particular tissue or organ is the term of stimuli responsive drug delivery. Synthesis of MSNs is through nickel, cobalt, ferrous and any other earth metals. Magnetic response mechanism is based on the drugs and the magnetic field that helps the drug to reach the particular

site of the body. The ideal form of MSNs is hyperthermia that is used in destruction of cancer cells and lowers the drug's destruction and their cellular toxicity in the normal cells.

5.6. Ultrasound response

The soundwave is not sensed by the human auditory nerve is the ultrasound that ranges from 20 KHz to 20MHz. It is widely used in the field of medicine for diagnosis and therapeutic purposes. Here US is used in two forms of low intensity focused ultrasound or high intensity focused ultrasound which depends on the disease condition and the targeted sites.

5.7. Adenosine triphosphate response

Concentration of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) in different organs and organelles are controlled. The ATP-sensitive aptamer are present between the two different single strands of DNA that is linked to the MSNs surface. ATP attacks, aptamer gets divided and it leaves the two different strands of unlinked DNA and leads to delivery of drug from the coated agents.

5.8. Hypoxia response

In diseased state, occurrence of hypoxia leads to the release of some of chemicals and enzymes such as reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate or reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide, nitro reductases, produces the cause of design hypoxia responsive DDS. For example, a nanocarrier unit filled with azobenzene derivatives exhibits breakdown of azo bonds which regulates drug delivery in hypoxia situations.

5.9. Electric response

Delivery of drug through the carrier by implementing the electric field externally in which the ionized groups of the compound gets electrolysed and this leads to liberation of drug at a definite rate.

6. BIOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR OF MSNs⁶

As previously noted, MSNs have been thoroughly researched to create novel smart CDDSs for biomedical and cancer therapeutic applications. However, when the research focuses on the clinical translation of these smart Nano systems, the nature of the interactions between them with biological medium (both in vitro and in vivo) is crucial. In general, two mechanisms can account for the toxicity of MSNs, Comparing MSNs to DSNs, the former have a higher surface area while the latter have pores, which results in reduced sialon density. Research has shown that complete surface modification eliminates the haemolytic action of MSNs. By decreasing the number of accessible sialon groups, functionalization of MSN surfaces can improve blood biocompatibility. Improving blood circulation time is crucial for in vivo application, and MSNs should be specifically accumulated in tumours to minimize negative effects caused by unintended and uncontrolled bioaccumulation in healthy organs. Numerous research teams have assessed MSNs' bio distribution in vivo. The unique properties of MSNs, including their porous structure for high loading capacity, chemical stability, surface functionality for stabilization, biocompatibility, controlled release with or without stimuli regulation, and specific cell targeting, offer many advantages to make them a novel class of Nano carriers for drug delivery. MSNs have demonstrated their capacity to encapsulate and regulate the release of a broad variety of bioactive compounds, including growth factors, siRNA, anticancer medications, DNA, and enzymes, for a variety of applications, such as imaging, biosensors, diabetes treatment, and MSNs in biocatalysts exhibit a high level of surface area and absorption capacity, as well as uniform pore distribution, excellent mechanical stability, and a functionalized surface. Phenyl Trimethyl group-functionalized MSNs have the ability to preferentially detect prostate specific antigen (PSA) in complicated biological samples, offering a low-cost and timely alternative for the detection of significant biomarkers. Thymolphthalein is a pH indicator.

Fig.4.MSNs adsorption drug loading¹³

7. APPLICATION (DIAGNOSTIC)⁷

7.1. Drug distribution via an MSNs-based carrier

A key requirement for developing an effective carrier for targeted medication delivery is the therapeutic molecules' capacity to be transported to the desired location without sacrificing their structure or functionalities. The cargo molecules must be released by the carrier in a controlled manner in order to accomplish this goal.

7.2. Using MSNs as bioimaging tools⁸

Because of MSNs hydrophilic surface, these mesoporous structures disperse evenly in aqueous solutions. In addition, MSNs large surface area and pore volume make it possible to create compartmental reservoirs with diverse capabilities, making them attractive choices for a range of medical imaging applications. The most popular non-invasive bioimaging methods are X-rays, ultrasound, magnetic waves, and chemical fluorescence. Chemical stability and a variety of physiological body circumstances are prerequisites for the employment of a chemical as a bioimaging agent. With a high blood circulation period and high contrast imaging capacity, the formulation should be in a colloidal solution both in vitro and in vivo. Up converting nanoparticles and quantum dot techniques are used in the bioimaging strategy based on MSNs.

7.3. Biosensors utilizing MSNs⁹

Because MSNs offer favorable features that enable them to be used as a sensor for detecting various analytes in both in vitro and in vivo settings, they have been thoroughly investigated in biosensor applications. Because of the special properties of nanostructures, such as their small size, high specific surface area, and adaptable chemistry, they can be employed as highly desirable sensors with high sensitivity for the detection of a variety of analytes in both in vitro and in vivo settings. Because of their high porosity and optical transparency, MSNs are a great choice among many nanoparticle-based biosensors for biosensing applications.

7.4. Treatment of disease

There have been reports of the potential for treating heart failure and Alzheimer's disease with MSN-based Nano carriers. According to reports, metal ions may accelerate the aggregation of A β and the production of ROS, which metal chelators can prevent. This could lead to an increase in the risk of Alzheimer's disease.

7.5. Tissue regeneration and wound healing¹⁰

MSN-based nanocarriers have demonstrated promising applications in wound healing and tissue regeneration, notwithstanding their rarity. ROS concentrations are typically higher at the sites of injury, where they can lead to fibrotic scarring, inflammation, and cellular senescence. It has been observed that wound healing is aided by ROS-responsive functionalized MSN-based nanocarriers. To create a highly adaptable tissue adhesive nanocomposite that scavenges reactive oxygen species, ultrasmall ceria nanocrystals were doped on the surface of amino functionalized MSNs. Strong tissue adhesion strength was provided by the ceria nanocrystals in the system, which also markedly sped up the healing process by improving skin appendage development and limiting scar formation.

7.6. Diagnostic procedures and imaging

To reduce systemic cytotoxicity, it's critical to monitor the focused and localized administration of chemotherapy drugs. To create Nano carriers that can deliver chemotherapy while also providing the ability to track the Nano carrier's bio distribution, a variety of ligands and molecules, including Chlorin e6, FITC, Hoechst, carbon dot, ⁶⁴Cu, fluorescein, and N,N-phenylenebis (salicylideneimine)dicarboxylic acid (Salphdc), have been functionalized to MSNs. In a urethane-induced lung cancer mouse model, for instance, Nano carriers made DOX-loaded ⁶⁴Cu-labeled MSNs gated with AuNPs could provide bio tools, such as PET imaging, to detect the presence of clinically relevant spontaneous lung tumors in addition to the NIR-triggered release of DOX and the synergistic effect of photothermal therapy in cancer therapy.

7.8. MSNs as a means of treating inflammation¹¹

For possible use in biomedical applications, MSNs have also been used as a vehicle for the delivery of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. To treat osteoarthritis, for instance, Jin et al. created celastrol-loaded MSNs. To create pH-dependent drug delivery systems, chitosan has been added to the MSNs. The proposed formulation demonstrated improved solubility and possible therapeutic action at pH [6.0], as well as increased stability at pH 7.4. MSNs loaded with ibuprofen were developed to alleviate musculoskeletal pain in a different investigation.

7.9. PDT, or photodynamic treatment¹²

One of the most recent developments in medicine is photodynamic treatment (PDT). PDT employs light to more effectively deliver the medication to the intended location. Comprising a photosensitizer that releases the medicine trapped inside the formulation or kills cells when activated by light, the formulation produces reactive oxygen species (ROS). Either directly produces ROS species or forces the cells to make them on their own, depending on the photosensitizer. Oxygen free radicals, or ROS, are extremely unstable within cells and react quickly, resulting in rapid action. Given that PDT is more applicable to cancer patients, it has had a significant impact on cancer treatment. Nevertheless, the generated ROS is extremely harmful to the cell. When cancer is treated, this ROS eventually causes the cells to die.

8. CONCLUSION¹³

In conclusion, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) represent a promising and versatile platform for advancing drug delivery systems in biomedical applications. Their unique structural properties, including high surface area and tunable pore sizes, facilitate efficient encapsulation and controlled release of therapeutic agents. The functionalization of MSNs, particularly with targeting ligands such as folic acid, enhances cellular uptake and improves the cytotoxicity of chemotherapeutic agents, demonstrating significant potential in cancer treatment. Furthermore, MSNs have shown efficacy in overcoming bacterial drug resistance, underscoring their relevance in addressing pressing medical challenges. Their biocompatibility and ease of modification broaden their applicability across therapeutic and diagnostic fields, highlighting their role at the forefront of Nano medicine. As ongoing research explores innovative combinations with other nanomaterials and smart drug delivery strategies, the future of MSNs in clinical applications looks promising. Collectively, the body of literature emphasizes the multifaceted roles of MSNs in enhancing drug delivery efficacy, paving the way for revolutionary treatment approaches in various medical disciplines. Continued exploration and development of MSNs are essential to fully realize their potential in improving patient outcomes and advancing therapeutic strategies.

9. REFERENCES:

- 1 Ahmed H, Gomte SS, Prathyusha E, Prabakaran A, Agrawal M, Alexander A. *Biomedical applications of mesoporous silica nanoparticles as a drug delivery carrier. Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology.* 2022 Oct 1;76:103729.
- 2 Tonbul H, Sahin A, Tavukcuoglu E, Ultav G, Akbas S, Aktas Y, Esendagli G, Capan Y. *Folic acid decoration of mesoporous silica nanoparticles to increase cellular uptake and cytotoxic activity of doxorubicin in human breast cancer cells. Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology.* 2021 Jun 1;63:102535.
- 3 Thi TT, Nguyen TN, Hoang DT, Nguyen DH. *Functionalized mesoporous silica nanoparticles and biomedical applications. Materials Science and Engineering: C.* 2019 Jun 1;99:631-56.

- 4 Bardhan M, Majumdar A, Jana S, Ghosh T, Pal U, Swarnakar S, Senapati D. Mesoporous silica for drug delivery: Interactions with model fluorescent lipid vesicles and live cells. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*. 2018 Jan 1;178:19-26.
- 5 Zhuang J, Yu Y, Lu R. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles as carrier to overcome bacterial drug resistant barriers. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2023 Jan 25;631:122529.
- 6 Jafari S, Derakhshankhah H, Alaei L, Fattahi A, Varnamkhasti BS, Saboury AA. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles for therapeutic/diagnostic applications. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2019 Jan 1;109:1100-11.
- 7 Sabio RM, Meneguín AB, Ribeiro TC, Silva RR, Chorilli M. New insights towards mesoporous silica nanoparticles as a technological platform for chemotherapeutic drugs delivery. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2019 Jun 10;564:379-409.
- 8 Nik AB, Zare H, Razavi S, Mohammadi H, Ahmadi PT, Yazdani N, Bayandori M, Rabiee N, Mobarakeh JI. Smart drug delivery: Capping strategies for mesoporous silica nanoparticles. *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*. 2020 Jun 1;299:110115.
- 9 Gupta J, Quadros M, Momin M. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles: Synthesis and multifaceted functionalization for controlled drug delivery. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 2023 Mar 1;81:104305.
- 10 Feng S, Zhang H, Xu S, Zhi C, Nakanishi H, Gao XD. Folate-conjugated, mesoporous silica functionalized boron nitride nanospheres for targeted delivery of doxorubicin. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*. 2019 Mar 1;96:552-60.
- 11 Narayan R, Nayak UY, Raichur AM, Garg S. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles: A comprehensive review on synthesis and recent advances. *Pharmaceutics*. 2018 Aug 6;10(3):118.
- 12 Eguílaz M, Villalonga R, Rivas G. Electrochemical biointerfaces based on carbon nanotubes-mesoporous silica hybrid material: Bioelectrocatalysis of hemoglobin and biosensing applications. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*. 2018 Jul 15;111:144-51.
- 13 Rawat N, Sandhya, Subaharan K, Eswaramoorthy M, Kaul G. Comparative in vivo toxicity assessment places multiwalled carbon nanotubes at a higher level than mesoporous silica nanoparticles. *Toxicology and industrial health*. 2017 Feb;33(2):182-92.